

and spiders. Stems of a tobacco cultivar containing 4% nicotine may be mixed with pyrimoxythion for root-zone application. Tobacco stems and leaves alone are effective if applied 5–6 days before the peak of emergence.

Five species of hymenopterous species have been found in Kwangtung: *Platygaster* sp. (polyembryonic), *Platygaster* sp. (monoembryonic), *Nenanastatus cinctiventris* Gir., *N. orientalis* Gir., and *Obtusiclava oryzae* Subba Rao. *Platygaster* (polyembryonic) usually predominates, but *Nenanastatus* increases to 70–80% during seedling and tillering stages of the late crop (both in seedbeds and in the field).

As much as 90% gall midge parasitization occurs in the late crop. Irrational insecticide application, however, kills

natural enemies and may encourage gall midge resurgence. Gall midge parasitization in the overwintering generation in wild rice reached 65% in 1976 investigations in San-Huan brigade, Hua County, Kwangtung. Parasitization reached 32–33% in the first and second generations of the early crop, but dropped to 2–5% in late-crop seedbeds (compared with 44% in untreated fields) because of frequent applications (4- to 5-day intervals) of methyl parathion-BHC and dimethoate. The order of toxicity to *Platygaster* sp. as contact poisons was pyrimoxythion > trichlorfon > dimethoate > 2, 5-dimethylphenyl-N-methylcarbamate > chlordimeform.

The growing of gall midge-resistant varieties such as Bao Tou San 2 and Qui Yang Nai 121 is being investigated.

Resistant varieties have been tested and biotype variations are being determined in cooperation with the International Rice Testing Program. Research indicates that resistance is antibiotic — under the same infestation conditions larvae were still in the first instar 7 days after hatching in Bao Tou San 2, but all larvae had molted into the second instar in a susceptible variety.

Preliminary experiments on the use of pheromone traps for monitoring and as a control measure are promising. An extract by dichloromethane of the virgin female attracts males at night. Large numbers of males and females have been caught in light trap-pheromone extract combinations. The sex pheromone is being purified and identified; it seems to be an ester. ■

Root-zone application of systemic insecticides for insect control in China

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Results of 5 years' experiments in South China indicated that root-zone application of systemic insecticides effectively controlled almost all potential insect pests of rice: the yellow stem borer *Tryporyza incertulas*, the striped stem borer *Chilo suppressalis*, the pink borer *Sesamia inferens*, the rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, the rice gall midge *Orseolia oryzae*, the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, the green leafhopper *Nephotettix* spp., the rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis*, and the rice root weevil *Echinocnemus squameus*.

In extensive trials of 14 compounds, 1 root-zone application of carbofuran granules at 1.5 kg a.i./ha effectively controlled gall midge, yellow stem borer, pink borer, rice thrips, green leafhopper, and brown planthopper. Root-zone carbofuran remained effective against borers 40–60 days; they remained effective against the brown planthopper 30 days after application. One application of carbofuran granules by

The effectiveness of thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate (Evisect) for the control of the yellow stem borer and rice thrips. Dosage: 1.5 kg a.i./ha. Root-zone application is better than broadcast.

soil incorporation in rice seedbeds gave good field control of 1 gall midge generation and 2 other pests. The rice seedlings carried the insecticide into the paddy after transplanting with no adverse effects on the egg-larval parasite *Platygaster* spp. This method of carbofuran application is popular among rice farmers in Kwangtung, Kiangsu, and other provinces.

Although carbofuran is a broad-spectrum insecticide, its effectiveness against the leaf folder is low. In fields with heavy leaf folder infestation, application of carbofuran mixed with padan, or dimehypo, or chlordimeform is recommended.

Nereistoxin made from a marine annelid has served as a base for a group of useful insecticides. When applied in the root-

zone, the nereistoxin derivatives padan, dimehypo, and thiocyclam hydrogen oxalate (“Evisect,” see photo) (San 1551) have recently been found to be good systemic insecticides for control of stem borers, leaf folder, and thrips. These compounds, selective contact and stomach insecticides, act as synaptic blocking agents. Their mode of action differs completely from those of organophosphorus and carbamate compounds. The long residual action of soil-applied padan — as long as 50 days after treatment — was outstanding for yellow borer control.

Most farmers in China still rely mainly on cultural practices and insecticides for pest control because biological control agents — including *Trichogramma*, *Bacillus thuringiensis*, spiders, and

ducks — possess limitations and have been used only in certain regions, and breeding for insect resistance is in its infancy. ■

Gall midge life cycle and plant injury in South China

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In Kwangtung Province, South China, the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* undergoes 9–10 overlapping generations a year to cause its greatest damage to the third irrigated rice crop. A life cycle is completed in 21–38 days.

The larvae feeding within the culm base cause the formation of galls or silver shoots. It is not clear whether feeding activity or a salivary gland substance by the maggot stimulates growth to form a gall. Gall formation is caused by the suppression of leaf primordial differentiation in the growing point and the development of radial ridges from the innermost leaf primordium, followed by leaf sheath elongation. This occurs in the tillering stage. After panicle initiation, larvae no longer cause damage because the growing point has changed (see figure). ■

Stage	Duration (days)	Status of gall formation	Diagram showing gall formation	Average length (mm) of the gall	Outer appearance of the rice plant	Type of gall
1st-instar larvae	Early period 1–3	Newly hatched larvae entering the growing point 1				
	Middle period 3–4	Oval-shaped chamber formed by the inner young leaf 2				
	Late period 5–6	Multiplication and thickening of the cells on the upper layer of the oval-shaped chamber 3				
2d-instar larvae	0.5	Multiplication and thickening of the sponge-shaped cells in the ova-shaped chamber 4		1.6		
	Middle & late period 1–1.5	A gall has completely formed 5				
3d-instar larvae	3–4	The length of the gall is equal to that of the insect body 6				
Pre-pupa	2	The gall begins to elongate 7		5.5		
Duration of pupae	1st stage pupae 1.4	The gall markedly elongates		9		
	2d stage pupae 1.4			28		
	3d stage pupae 1.4			53		
	4th stage pupae 1.4	96				
	5th stage pupae 1.4	105				

Diagram showing the process of gall formation and the characteristics of the injury due to the rice gall midge. Observations were made on the injury of rice seedlings by 3d generation of rice gall midge in Du-yan Commune, Sin-hui County, Kwangtung Province, China, 1976.

Ants — a natural enemy of *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis* larvae in dryland rice

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In dryland areas of Batangas province, Philippines, where 1 crop of rice/year is grown, the leaf folder *Chaphalocrosis medinalis* (Guenee) is the most important insect pest attacking the aboveground portions of the rice plant. But investigation of folded leaves in the 1978 season revealed very few larvae. Possible explanations were sought through field observations. Ants were found to leave their nests in underground tunnels and

Adult of *Diacamma* sp. [120 X](Hymenoptera:Formicidae). IIRI.